

METHODOLOGY FOR CONDUCTING AN EXPERIMENTAL TEST ON THE ORIENTATION OF STUDENTS TO PROFESSIONAL SELECTION USING NATIONAL TRADITIONS

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Annotation: this article covers the pedagogical foundations of vocational guidance of students in general secondary schools. The article also covers the scientific and theoretical foundations of conducting the BO'uicha experimental and test work to direct students to the profession.

Keywords: education system, profession, experience test, methodology, circle.

This year, our President Sh. During his visit to Fergana, Mirziyoyev gave special instructions to the Ministry of public education. The president specifically touched on the issues of employment of young people, their orientation to the profession, noting that from the new school year from the 7th grade, students should be directed to the profession. The president's Minister of public education, Sh. According to the instruction given to shermatov, from the 2020-2021 school year from the 7th grade, students will be directed to the profession, and it will be determined exactly what kind of profession they will have. Until the 8th, 9th, 10th grade, they are trained in a profession of their choice. In 10 classes, certificates are issued that give them the right to work. In 11th grade, however, students will also be able to earn a monthly salary by working formally in businesses and organizations at the same time. Governors and heads of the regional sector are responsible for the employment of graduates of 11 classes.¹

From this instruction, it can be seen that youth employment, professional orientation are one of the main tasks of the policy of our state. Of great importance in this regard is the orientation of school graduates to the profession, the choice of the right profession based on their talent.

It is known that the prosperity, social, political, economic stability of any society depends on the high level of development of the mental and moral potential of its citizens. After all, in the spiritual renewal of our society, in the formation of a socially oriented market economy, the national issue of Personnel Training, the construction of a democratic collective state, which ensures its integration into the world community, plays an important role as a priority criterion.

¹ Goziev E., Mamedov K. Occupational psychology. - T.: Özmu, 2003. 156-b

As a human child matures, he plunges into science and enlightenment. He also takes the initial lesson from school. But teaching young people who are the owners of our future it is natural that some of the problems associated with teaching them are making a person think today. This is because the modern society continues to have a reputation for mature knowledgeable staff.

The initial and at the same time extremely important stage of the process of professional formation involves the choice of the future profession, that is, the period until the arrival of a specific professional decision. It is clear that the level of preparation of young people for the choice of a profession is not just an attachment to age characteristics, it does not form on its own by a certain age. The choice of profession of young people should be prepared and brought up through pedagogical-psychological knowledge, skills, qualifications, as well as the influence of society. In this process, a person is required to have knowledge of the profession. Therefore, it is necessary to arm students with knowledge about the world of professions and to develop practical skills and qualifications. To do this, it is necessary to provide manuals on professions, handouts. Only then will we have the opportunity to consciously send students-young people to the profession, avoiding various difficulties, conflicts, obstacles that arise in the process of choosing a profession.²

A technology teacher must communicate information about the types of professions and labor to students in the process of technological education, linking them to specific topics. A special place among classes, which are held based on the interests of students, is occupied by circles related to specific professions. Such circles are carried out in most cases by teachers of Labor and professional education. These include such circles as technical-creativity, young artists, young technologists, Young Physicists. The teacher has the opportunity to systematically work on the development of students' abilities in such circles, such as drafting, technical-creativity, inventiveness. The technology teacher should allocate a special place in his work activities for pedagogical-psychological diagnosis. In the process of pedagogical-psychological diagnosis, the teacher, in cooperation with the school leadership and psychologist, officials of the educational and production institution and professional colleges, must determine the proportion between the chosen profession of each student and his personal qualities.

² Makhmudova.D. "Ensuring continuity and continuity between elements of pedagogical activity related to the orientation of students in the profession". Journal of public education. Issue # 3, pp. 57-58.

The teacher of technology should carry out his activities related to the vocational guidance of students, embodied in the activities of class leaders, science teachers, school leadership and psychologist, parents, neighborhood activists, administration of vocational colleges in the area. Labor room, laboratory and workshops are also of particular importance in the proper orientation of students to the profession. The teacher of Labor science should pay special attention to equipping them on the basis of modern requirements, since the knowledge, understanding and imagination of a particular type of Labor and profession in students is formed here at first. As you know, love for labor and professions is formed in the composition of beliefs, all educational disciplines. Therefore, special attention to interdisciplinary engagement is required in technological education classes. It is of important pedagogical importance to harmonize the activities of the labor teacher regarding the socialization of students by vocational guidance with the work of teachers and class leaders of various educational disciplines in this area. *For this:*

- make the most of the opportunities of various academic disciplines, science clubs and extracurricular and extracurricular activities;
- achieve socialization by directing students to the profession with the help of technological knowledge, universal knowledge and professional skills;
- to ensure that students complete academic assignments with a high level of social relevance aimed at a particular goal;
- to achieve the formation of the interests of students on the basis of a differentiated approach to various areas of Labor and profession, which are relevant for the life of society;
- to establish cooperation of school teachers, firms, production enterprises, creative teams, professional colleges and diagnostic centers in order to direct students to a worthy profession. As a result of such cooperation, it is possible to carry out the promotion of professions with a high level of social significance among students.³

A technology teacher school practicing psychologist must carry out the following in the process of his professional activity:

- ❖ *providing information about the demographic properties of professions;*
- ❖ *to organize tips of a pedagogical-psychological nature for guiding students to the profession;*

³ Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova "Use of Innovative Technologies In the Educational Process" Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;

- ❖ *formation of stable interests in students in certain professions, taking into account their personal qualities;*
- ❖ *to acquaint students with famous personalities who gained fame as a result of their professional activities and their contributions to the development of society and humanity;*
- ❖ *informing students about the role of professions in the development of economic, social, spiritual aspects of society;*
- ❖ *conduct conversations with parents of students on the orientation of their children to a worthy profession;*
- ❖ *informing students of the negative consequences of choosing the wrong profession;*
- ❖ *create favorable conditions for students to form and test initial universal and professional skills;*
- ❖ *in order to guide students to the right profession, to study their personality, type of Labor and interests in professions;*

When choosing a profession, the propaganda work carried out by the school practitioner-psychologist also has its significance. Because not all trainees can come to a clear idea when choosing a profession. There are different reasons for this in itself. In this place, I conducted round tables, questionnaire surveys with students of the graduating classes of the school where I work. For example: when to start yunaltizing the profession? the answer to the question "What is the difference?" was received in the following diagram. 57% of students believe that vocational guidance should be started from school. 22% of students believe this should start at kindergarten, and 14% believe that the selection phase should start at Colledge.

To the question of who should carry out vocational guidance, the answer of readers was distributed as follows: psychologists (32%), teachers (28%) and employers themselves (13%). In addition, 13% expressed the opinion that this work should be entrusted to the Center for employment of the population. The participants who chose the "other" answer option, NNG 14%, gave the following answer options: parents, the person himself, all of the above, parents together with teachers, it is necessary that many structures in this matter have an integrated approach and partnership.

During my career, I spent a couple of such photographs and questionnaires. It turns out that the importance of the activities of teachers and practicing psychologists in the choice of professions for schoolchildren is very great.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that directing our young people to the right profession, I would like to emphasize once again that this is one of the most important vases. It is a law that does not require proof that a person, by choosing the right profession, gives a huge welcome to his family, society.

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